

Effect of exchange rate, inflation rate and interest rate on Balance of Payment (BOP): a research from India and Bangladesh

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Abstract

Exchange rate remains an important element in international macroeconomics; its impact is evidence various currency disasters in many countries and gets attractions for the economists around the worlds. Exchange rate has been proved its nature in evaluating the state financial situation. It is a proportional research of Balance of Payment (BOP) of two nations: Bangladesh and India. This text mentioned that BOP be supposed to be constant. It must not be in debit (Deficit) and in credit (surplus) as in both situations, it will be adverse. Thus this study evaluate the variation in three important rates of any country that is 1) interest rate, 2) inflation rate, and 3) foreign exchange rate on BOP. Outcome describes that inflation and exchange rate will have favorable impact mean while interest rate will have adverse impact on BOP in both countries.

Keywords

Exchange Rate, Interest Rate, Inflation Rate, Balance of Payments (BOP).

1. Introduction

Balance of payments (BOP) provides the detail knowledge of the country demand and supply of currency. BOP must remain constant, it should not be either deficit or surplus as in both situations it is not favorable for a country. BOP could also utilize to determine the economy of the country in the worldwide economic rivalry. Furthermore, the impact of ups and down in balance of trade will be result in evaluating of balance of payments (BOP) of country. BOP introduces methodology which helps to determine the payments made and receipts during certain period of time of the country from other countries in private and public sectors. Consequently, equation of BOP is receipts for example exports, attendance of the foreigner for tourism which make payments in country, remittance from oversee local resident, gift and grant got from different countries in the form of cash, or capital assets and payments made for import of different items and instruments, purchase of oversee services, and gifts made to other countries. To balance this equation (receipts and payments), from last couple year's government's show more interest to correctly perform the economic strategy to determine export to different countries, and cut down imports at similar time. Whereas, in those countries which having the stability in their policies, this will be achievable easily in long term macroeconomic policies of their balance of payments goals. In opposition, many developing nations having with poor application of that strategy will result in adverse growth. In this research, we are matching the BOP of Bangladesh and India by using the many variables for example: exchange rate, inflation rate and interest rate. Since several years, BOP of both the countries has been in deficit for a longer time. Because of the downfall in the currency of the country's capital account tends to be in surplus If the capital account remains surplus it has a major impact on the BOP of a country which is mention as follow

- The domestic crisis of the country has a great effect on BOP. The economists try to overcome these issues.
- The economists deploy the methods of for the development of exports and betterment of the BOP and also cut down the exchange rate.
- International Monetary Fund (IMF) gives loan either short term or long term to developing countries to float their economy, but it will have a negative impact such as, repayments schedule which is made in installments, it drive the currency of the country toward decline which result in financial crisis.
- Tendency from rural areas to urban areas drive to more growth in industries and increase the export proportion which helps BOP in turn of surplus.
- Foreign investment (FI) also has a major impact on the BOP. Inflow of FI will result in surplus and outflow will create the deficit.
- Corruption is also major impact. Due to it, foreign investor reluctant to invest in country and it will result in negative impact on the BOP.
- In this new tenure, multinational bank loan facilities increase in the economy because of increase in mark up on deposits, and inflow of FI and it will result in positive impact on BOP because to inflow of cash in the country.
- The interest rate is low in those countries because of type of Debt, Structure of debt (Long term or short term or it repayment schedule), and strategy for the holding the foreign reserve.
- Exchange rate policies have a major impact on the exports of the country. Other factors which influence the most of exports of the country that is Black Market which greater or lesser the demand and supply of dollar

- Foreign trade also plays a vital role to maintain BOP of the country.
- From the research it was concluded that efficient fiscal policy utilized to boost level of saving.

2. Methodology

2.1. Balance of Payments

The BOP shows the receipts and payments which is book of transactions with the world. If a country inflation rate increase, it will have adverse impact on the economy.

2.3. Foreign Exchange Rate

Exchange rate can be defined as such unit currency of a country that is paid to buy unit of the other country currency. Factors which impact on the exchange rate the most which are as such:

- Mark up rate
- Inflation factor
- Political instability of the country
- Internal Factors of a country (sectarian issue, races, terrorism, civil war etc.)
- Governance Quality of a country

Exchange rate influences a lot on the BOP. Exchange rate of Bangladesh and India is very low which has adverse impact on BOP. From this study, we come to conclusion that exchange rate play a vital role in the balance of payments. Balance of payments is the list of transactions with the other country which demonstrate the receipts and payments with other country for the certain period of time.

2.4. Inflation Rate

Inflation rate knows as general rise in price which can be evaluate by general purchasing power of normal personal. Inflation evaluates by comparing the same sets of things at different time (past and present). Increase in inflation rate will have a negative impact on economy. Inflation will have a huge impact on the stander of living of normal person. They have to pay more to buy the same things or services as compare with the previous purchased. Inflow of cash should be increase as compare to increase in inflation otherwise it would be harder to survive for the normal personal

3. Results

3.1. Regression Analysis of Bangladesh

For this study, I collect data from International Financial Statistics (IFS) for inflation, exchange rate, BOP, and interest rate. By evaluating the regression between BOP, and three rates interest rate, foreign rate, and inflation rate, and I came to conclusion which is mentioned as below:

BOP =35, inflation rate +25.4, interest rate -35.9, foreign exchange rate +97.10

Table 1. Regression Analysis of Bangladesh

Predictor	Coef	St. Dev	T value	P
Constant	34.7	160.0	0.11	0.720
Inflation rate	25.423	8.326	2.02	0.007
Interest rate	-35.86	15.07	-1.47	0.036
Foreign exchange rate	97.10	2.358	6.10	0.000

$S = 134.4, R^2=81.0\%, R^2dj =77.7\%$

$R^2 =71.0\%$ demonstrates a good relationship between independent variables (inflation rate, foreign exchange rate, and interest rate) and dependent variable (BOP). Coefficient of inflation is 25.423, foreign exchange=97.21 which shows positive relationship and have a major influence on BOP. Although interest rate has negative value but has a great influence on BOP. Nil hypothesis value should be rejected for independent variables. The outcome from the ANOVA(Fisher Model) for Bangladesh shows in the Table2

Table 2. ANOVA for Bangladesh

Source	DF	SS	MS	F
Regression	3	1770284	442463	25.69 (0.000)
Error	22	415573	18175	
Total	25	2185857		

The high value of F statistic and extremely low p value (given in parenthesis below F value) support the regression model.

To support the regression model, very low P value (given in parenthesis right side by F value) and F statistic

3.2. Regression Analysis of INDIA

To evaluate the regression among BOP and interest rate, exchange rate, inflation rate following equation is create which is mentioned below:

$BOP = -537, Inflation\ rate + 142, interest\ rate -191, foreign\ exchange +97.1$

$R^2=78.21\%$ demonstrates that the model is good enough. The coefficient of inflation rate and exchange rate are 133.40 and 97.20 retrospectively which have optimistic impact on BOP and it has a great impact on the BOP. The outcome from the ANOVA(Fisher Model) for India also are demonstrate in table no 4.

Table 3. Regression Analysis of India

Variable	Coef	St Dev	T value	P
BOP	-572.3	983.6	-0.44	0.473
Inflation rate	131.20	77.11	2.54	0.086
Interest rate	-197.	1104.3	-1.76	0.066
Foreign Exchange rate	98.20	13.131	5.81	0.000

$S = 836.7, R^2= 78.2\%, R^2 (adj) = 74.3\%$

Table 4. ANOVA for India

Source	DF	SS	MS	F
Regression	3	54200325	13550088	18.42 (0.000)

Error	27	16054778	698036
Total	30	702550103	

To support the regression model, very low P value (given in parenthesis below F value) and F statistic.

3.3. Analysis of Bangladesh’s BOP over Last Couple of Years

Due to instability of political and domestic circumstance of the country these factors influenced a lot on the BOP, inflation was low in 1986 to 1997 and it getting higher from 1998 to 2007 and reach at the top then decline in between 1998 to 1999 and inflation rate in 2004 was at the value 4.32% which is as low in last 25 years. The rate was changed in 2007 due to political instability in country and disorder position of law and order. The BOP was greatly influenced by coefficient of inflation which is rate=25.423%.it shows positive influence on the BOP. There is change in the value of inflation by 1% because of change in the value of BOP and it will result in 25.423%.The graph demonstrates there is no correlation consists of in value of inflation.

Figure 1. Inflation rate of Bangladesh

Impact of interest rate on BOP:

If Inflation increases, then the interest rate will also rise. The higher interest rate will attract the stakeholders to invest in such country. The graph mentions the value of interest rate decrease from 1981 to 1989 due to decrease in inflation rate. In 1999 the value of interest rate is high that was 13.44% and then it declined up to 2006 and after it started to increase and in 2009 it was 8.4% and the foreign direct investment value increased from 2006 to 2007. The coefficient of interest rate=-38.71 mentions its adverse effect on the BOP. 2% modification in value of interest rate will impact in the decline in value of BOP by 38.71%. The graph mention there is no correlation consisted of in value of interest in figure 2.

Figure2. Interest rate of Bangladesh

The below graph mentions the worth of Bangladeshi currency unit demised in previous years as compare to US Dollar. In 2009, the Bangladeshi currency value impaired to 71.21 as compare to US Dollar due to instability of political and inflation increase by 13%. Value of coefficient is 10.218 that shows exchange rate have strong correlation with BOP. If there is 1% modification in value will cause 10.218% impact on BOP. The graph mentions there is no correlation exists in value term of foreign exchange rate.

Figure 3. Foreign exchange rate of Bangladesh

3.4. Analysis of India’s BOP Over Last Years

The inflation was at top in 1991 that was 13.8% from the previous years and remained stable in 2003 and 2004 that was 3.8% and again rise in 2008 but that rising rate was lesser than Bangladesh’s inflation rate. The value of coefficient 132.30 demonstrates that inflation rate have direct correlation with the BOP of India. Inflation does have great influence on BOP of India as compare to Bangladesh. The graph mentions that there was no correlation consists in value of inflation.

Figure 4. Inflation rate of India

The interest rate remained steady from 1983 to 1987 and greater than before in 1987 and after that again it was steady in 2000. The interest rate increased in 1997 and dropped at its peak value of 13.45 and then decline yet again in year 2005 and following this it happened to raised again in 2009 that paying attention in additional to extra FDI as compare to Bangladesh’s

financial system. The value of coefficient was -197.2 that demonstrated negative correlation with the BOP, that mentioned 2% raised in interest rate value would demised in value of BOP by 197.2. The graph demonstrated that there was no relationship consists in value of interest.

Figure 5. Interest rate of India

The value of Indian currency unit decline as compare to US Dollar but not as much as the Bangladeshi currency in past couple of years. The value of Indian currency unit is 42.41 at 2007 the depreciated value was lesser than Bangladeshi currency at similar year is 60.52 as compare to US Dollar. The value of coefficient 97.2 mentioned positive correlation with BOP. The graph mentioned that there is no correlation consists in value of foreign exchange rate.

YEARS WISE DOLLAR RATE

Figure 6. Foreign exchange rate of India

4. Conclusion

BOP gives us knowledge in depth regarding country’s currency supply and demand. BOP plays a vital role in economy of a country. After this research we came to conclude that inflation and foreign exchange rate will have positive impact on the BOP of both the countries and interest rate will results in negative impact on them. It was also evaluated from this research that supervision of both countries need assist to resolve the issues for shakiness of BOP. For such Countries like Bangladesh and India, it is very important to having proper evaluating systems attached with appropriate macroeconomic strategies. Such strategies should be introduced which attracted inflow of cash from the foreigners e.g. remittance etc. Moreover, these developed monitoring at different strategic levels (Government or public sector) (e.g.

planning and development department, Research department, central banks (state banks), Ministries of economies, foreign affairs commerce, trade, and industries, Departments of statistics and budgets) can play management body role for the imposing the economic policies. Similarly, provide reasonable atmosphere for foreigner to invest in the country on consistent basis such as stability of political situation, law and order positions, incentive for tourism in country etc. This will help in achieving balance of payments targets and by having steady exchange rates, this will help in longer period of time.

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